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*«ПОЧЕМУ?» – ЭТО ВОПРОС О КОТОРЫЙ ДО СИХ ПОР
РАЗБИВАЛАСЬ ВСЯ ЛОГИКА, ВСЯ ФИЛОСОФИЯ, ВСЯ НАУКА.*

ЭРИХ МАРИЯ РЕМАРК

**НАУЧНО-ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИЙ ИНСТИТУТ «ФИЗИКИ
РЕЗОНАНСНЫХ ЯДЕРНЫХ РЕАКЦИЙ» ЯВЛЯЕТСЯ НАУЧНЫМ
УЧРЕЖДЕНИЕМ, ОСУЩЕСТВЛЯЮЩИМ
ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ, ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ НАУЧНЫЕ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ РАЗРАБОТКИ В
ОБЛАСТИ НАУКИ, ТЕХНИКИ, КУЛЬТУРЫ И ПРОСВЕЩЕНИЯ.**

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THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN ENHANCING THE SPIRITUALITY OF WOMEN

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of education in improving women's spirituality and the opportunities created for women in the field of education.

Keywords: woman, spirituality, education, family, society.

Our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized that «it is necessary to further strengthen the foundations of the family, which is sacred to us, to create an atmosphere of peace, harmony and mutual respect in homes, and to fill spiritual and educational work with a clear content.» The great enlightener Abdurauf Fitrat wrote: «In order to raise our children to be good-natured, first of all, the mothers of the nation must receive education and knowledge.» When we talk about building the foundation of the Third Renaissance, creating a new spiritual space in society, we must carry out these works in harmony with the spirituality of fathers, mothers, and teachers. Today we live in an open society. We must use this opportunity correctly and assimilate progressive ideas. However, we must be careful not to lose our identity and vices that undermine our national image.»

Respect and honor for women, the pillars of family and society, the beauty of our lives, has always been a great value for our people. In the current development of our homeland, in the life of the family and society, women occupy an important place and position. In particular, our motto «Attention to women — attention to the future» is not in vain. Currently, most women are serving the welfare of society as a socially active stratum with high intelligence, influential secular knowledge and skills. If we look back at the years of independence, special attention has been paid to increasing the social activity of women in society. The rules required in the current era regarding the

treatment of women are imbued with the noble ideals of Islam and have existed in our people for a long time [1; p. 65]

encouraged women to engage in work that is appropriate to their nature and personality. At the same time, women are becoming a major social force in our society.

All events held in our country today cannot take place without the participation of our women. In particular, thousands of scientists and virtuous women work in the fields of science, education, and culture, who have their own position and worthy jobs in the development of society. In this regard, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, IA Karimov, specifically touched upon the issue of women and girls, saying, «Today, in the world of education, there is a special issue called the interests of women and girls, and it is not for nothing that great importance is attached to studying it and finding a solution. If women are not given sufficient attention, such a society will have no future.» As an explanation of these sentences, we have enough opportunities today to involve our women and girls in education and to obtain higher education.

The main goal of our higher education is to form a well-rounded young generation with comprehensive potential, a broad outlook, and intellectual abilities. Only if our mothers have sufficient knowledge and potential can they harmoniously educate and train their children. The role of our women in educating and training children is superior to that of men. This is because from the moment a child is born until he reaches adulthood, he first understands the social relations and norms existing in society through his mother [page 2.38].

It is not enough for a modern woman to simply read, write, and do arithmetic; she is faced with the problem of the quality of education, which requires her to constantly work independently, constantly improve her knowledge. Therefore, it is necessary not only to attract our daughters to education, but also to provide educational benefits to our daughters who do not have higher education from the state budget, or to train them in all types of professions in special «Monocenters». Our women are now contributing to the family budget. This is certainly a good situation. However, we must emphasize that in some cases, women are becoming the main breadwinners of their families.

We can observe an increase in the regulatory function of women in the family. This can also be a factor in the emergence of a number of social problems in the family. There are also various categories of women in our society who are socially disadvantaged. Our President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev is paying special attention to making our women and girls in need of social assistance active today, educating them in difficult situations, making them professionally skilled, and overcoming their problems on their own, and this is our priority goal as social workers.

If we compare our time with the past, the freedom, equality of rights and opportunities of our women today is remarkable. Today we will consider the existing benefits for our women. In particular, additional state grants and preferential loans are provided to women and girls when they enter education; women from low-income families, girls who are raised in single-parent families or who need social protection when both parents have died, women in need of social protection who have died and are raising a minor child alone, women from needy families with disabilities are given a recommendation letter by the Ministry of Neighborhood and Nuroniy Support, and these categories also belong to the «Women's Book». «Women's Book» covers our women and girls over 30 years old. Support mainly includes (financial, in-kind, provision of medicines, support with funds for surgical procedures). A quota of 4% can be obtained for HEIs.

In addition, Decree PF-5938 of February 18, 2020 «On measures to further support the mahalla institute for improving the social and spiritual environment in society and bringing the system of working with families and women to a new level» was adopted. It also focuses on providing social and legal assistance to women in need and in difficult social situations, women with disabilities, improving women's employment and working conditions, and involving women in family entrepreneurship and crafts in rural areas.

It is worth noting that on September 2, 2019, the Law on «Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men» was adopted, and Article 5 of it prohibits discrimination on the basis of gender, that is, in every type of activity, our women can work in any profession they want and build their careers like men. Article 58 of the new edition of our Constitution, which is currently being updated, states that women and men have equal rights. The state provides women and men with equal rights and opportunities in managing public and state affairs, as well as in other areas of public and state life. Well, in fact, there is a certain difference in the success of male and female leaders. As a result of extensive research, the famous Danish scientist F. Denmark came to the conclusion that women are more likely to rely on democratic principles, especially in human relations, voluntariness, and management. And these indicators represent a positive factor in a certain sense.

More than half of the members of 14 major trade unions in our country, which include more than 7 million workers, employees, and students, are women. We can see that in public administration, our women and girls holding the positions of «Deputy», «Minister», «Senator», «Deputy Minister», «Academician», «Entrepreneur», «Director» are a clear example of gender equality. The 2030 Equality Strategy covers issues such as ensuring equal rights and quality education for all, ensuring girls' access to higher education, and preventing violence. Starting from the 2023 academic year, 200 billion soums will be allocated annually to fully cover the contract fees of all women studying

for a master's degree from the budget, and at least 300 targeted quotas will be allocated annually for women to conduct scientific research at doctoral level. [Page 3.78]

It is planned to adopt a program to support women's education for 2022–2026. In 2021, within the framework of the women's entrepreneurship program, more than a thousand women were allocated 2 trillion in loans and subsidies for more than 200 thousand projects within the framework of family entrepreneurship, and 320 thousand women received permanent jobs. In 2021, 190 thousand women were trained in a profession. In addition, more than 4 thousand women are being allocated funds for the initial payment of housing. Human dignity is rising to higher levels from year to year. From July 1, 2020, a list of self-employed persons has been formed. In this regard, nursing work for our women is considered a type of self-employment activity. This activity is carried out by persons with higher education in secondary medical or higher nursing and registered in the relevant information system.

In each region, the self-government bodies have established an electronic system called the «Single Register of Social Protection». This system will form a list of low-income families, unemployed women and girls, and single women in need of social assistance residing in the MFY in each district. Through this process, women and girls in the neighborhood will actively support our needy women and girls in every way. This support will include social psychological, legal, ensuring a healthy lifestyle, identifying similar or more serious problems with the quality of medical and social services, and providing targeted assistance.

In conclusion, we can say that we need to take into account the aspirations and abilities of our educated and working women and girls, to continue their activities in society in an integral and harmonious way with men, and to expand their opportunities. Protecting the rights and interests of our women and increasing their social and political activity in our society is a reasonable strategy.

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